

Study the effect of notches on bending fatigue strength of 2024 aluminum sheets

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Abstract

In the present study, the effect of holes on the curvature fatigue strength of 2024 aluminum sheets. Has been studied by taking a model of this type and cutting it into models with the dimensions required for testing and by using a central hole as the main variable by making a central whole (CH) with a diameter of (1mm). The device used in this research is a Reversed bending machine of type HI-TECH from a British origin, all tests were done at a constant stress ratio ($R = -1$), a rotational speed of 6000 rpm and a frequency (100 Hz). The study was practically and theoretically (using the ANSYS15.0 program). The results showed that stress is affected by the presence of holes and we notice increased stress in the samples that contain holes more than the core samples that do not contain holes and thus we notice that fatigue strength decreases in the samples that contain a central hole by (32%) of the core samples by the practical side on the theoretical side, strength of fatigue less than percentage (43.7%). The yield strength was found by tensile test equal to (73.6 MPa) and the ultimate tensile strength (195.2 MPa) as for the hardness value (59.7). Also, from the results obtained, it appears that streaking acts as stress centers, thereby increasing stress and thereby reducing the number of cycles and consequently failure.

Keywords: Aluminum alloy; Notch sensitivity; Strength reduction factor; Fatigue

1. Introduction

The cost resulting from sudden failures of various structures and mechanical parts, both economically and humanly, can sometimes be quite massive. Therefore, studies on total failure have taken a wide range of research and studies in the scientific and industrial fields. The emergence and progression of fatigue cracks in the wings and feathers of different aircraft leads to fatal failures. The onset of fatigue initiation or the onset of fatigue cracking appears as slippage on the face of the model and after a period of fatigue life becomes fixed and cannot be removed and with increasing number of cycles of loads, these slippage deepens and then cracks begin to form, and cracks in the stressful body can grow and progress in association The three phases. There is sufficient evidence that many engineering structures contain pre-established defects and these defects arise during plumbing or manufacturing, and therefore speculation begins with the beginning of fatigue and its growth from these defects in the metals used in the manufacture of hulls and aircraft vehicles. As the progression of fatigue cracking occurs very quickly, and for this reason, the onset of fatigue plays an important role in predicting the life of these compounds. And the growth of the fissure in a region where the region of the stress factor and low stress factor is very required because of this importance in determining the required age for these devices, therefore this region is the most controllable for determining the age range of fatigue that concerns aircraft. One of the basic requirements for any engineering structure is that it does not fail during Shelf life, so most of the engineer's skill is concentrated in realizing that there are several potential patterns of failure and in realizing how to prevent them [1]. The main patterns of mechanical failure that pertain to the designer as well as failure due to environmental corrosion can be listed as follows [2].

- (Elastic Buckling)

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- (Excessive elastic deformation)
- (Plastic deformation)
- (Creep)
- (Cracking)

The phenomenon of failure due to fatigue is described as the process of forming cracks, and its growth to an unstable measurement ends in sudden failure entirely due to the exposure of the parts to periodic stresses, and the failure sometimes occurs with a change in the amount of load without a change in direction [3]. This failure is one of the most common types of failures in structures and mechanical parts [4-5].

The researchers studied (Qasim Bader, Emad Kadum, 2014) [6] the effect of the slitting (v) shape on the fatigue life in steel made from AISI 1037. Fatigue samples were made according to the specifications of the device used and made a (V) slit at different angles which are (30, 45, 90) degree and depth was (0.5, 2) mm. The study was practically and theoretically (using the ANSYS14.0 program), while the process was on a (Cantilever rotating-bending fatigue testing) at room temperature and frequency (50 Hz) and ($R = -1$), in this work the age of fatigue was verified The bending of the notched samples and thus the mathematical form of the formula for the fatigue life of samples was obtained. Note that in most cases it was found that the expected fatigue life was lower compared to the experimental values for all types of notched samples, this may be due to the fact that the fatigue life was predicted on the basis of the greatest stress in the notched section.

The researcher (D. W. Draket, 2015) [7] studied the effect of streaking and fatigue resistance, and many types of internal and external streaks have been studied in various forms. The factors controlling the slitting resistance were discussed, either from constant resistance or fatigue resistance, and it was found that the increase in the yield rate will usually increase the fixed efficiency of the slitting samples, but this increase may be limited by the ability of the material to react. It has been suggested that the use of high-resistance aluminum alloys in aircraft structures may produce a significant reduction in the structural weight of the same fixed resistance, but this may be accompanied by a decrease in fatigue resistance to the structures.

The researcher (Shaima Abdul Khader Hamza, 2018) [8] studied the effect of fixed and variable capacitance loads on the fatigue life of a low carbon steel alloy, the sample dimensions are of a length of (88.9 mm) and a width (30.1625 mm) and peripherally shortened from the middle, Fixed and variable capacity fatigue tests were performed using an Avery 7305 type device which operates by a 1420 rpm reverse-curving method. The higher the projected stress, the fewer cycles needed to fail, that is, the less fatigue life. In the case of fixed loads, fatigue life is greater compared to variable loads, where the number of turns required for failure is greater, and therefore the time required to form and grow the incision is greater.

The researchers studied (J. M. G. Martinez, et.al., 2019) [9] the effect of the size of the geometry on the prediction of the fatigue life of aluminum holes with small holes using critical distance methods. The wires used in the study are made of aluminum alloy 6201-T81. Servo-hydraulic testing machines were used with frequency (20 Hz) and ($R = -1$). Surround and V-Notch grooves, circular and many types of grooves were used. This research has been studied in theory (using FEM) and in practice. The LM obtained the best results by looking at all the small holes together, all expectations showed good adherence in this way with (84% for TH and (92%) for BH. The results of prediction of fatigue life in the small holes using the TCD method were satisfactory.

On this paper, the study of Notches and their effect on the resistance of the curvature of fatigue to aluminum sheets 2024, in practice and theory, using the program (ANSYS-Workbench) and by shedding the alternating stress of fatigue samples at a stress ratio ($R = -1$).

2. Experimental Work

2.1. Material Selection

Aluminum alloy (2024-0) with a thickness of (2.5 mm) is used in this study. It is one of the second series alloys with the basic alloy elements (Al. Cu. Mg). The main properties of this series are heat treatment and high strength at room temperature and also in degrees of High temperature. The Table (1) Chemical composition of aluminum alloy (AA2024) and its comparison with standard composition and Table (2) Real and standard mechanical, physical, and aluminum alloy properties (AA2024).

Table 1 Chemical composition of aluminum alloy (AA2024) and its comparison with standard composition [10]

Element (wt %) / Material	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Cr	Zn	Ti	Al
Standard	0.5Max	0.50 Max	3.8-4.9	0.3-0.9	1.2-1.8	0.1	0.25 Max	0.15Max	Bal.
Measured	0.131	0.260	4.49	0.61	1.32	0.006	0.04	0.08	Bal.

Table 2 Real and standard mechanical, physical, and aluminum alloy properties (AA2024) [10]

	Tensile strength (σ_y) (MPa)	Yield strength (MPa)	Ultimate Tensile strength (σ_u) (MPa)	Elongation (EI %)	Hardness Vickers (HV)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)
Standard Value	75		185	20	47	69
Actual Value	73.6		195.2	18.8	59.7	----

2.2. Tensile Test

Samples of the tension test were manufactured using (Water Jet) device, according to the dimensions specified according to the international standard [ASTMB557M] for the aluminum samples as shown in Figure (1). The test was carried out on a computer-equipped (SANS-Universal Testing Machine) tensile testing device located at Mosul University / Mechanical Engineering Department laboratories as shown in Figure (2), and it is an automated device with a capacity of (100) tons to shed a slowly increasing tension load (Monotonic Load) on the samples, and the examination was conducted at a displacement control rate of (0.3mm / min) until failure occurred. I calculated engineering stress and strain using the following relationships [11].

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A_o} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{\Delta L}{L} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Figure 1 Standard Dimensions of Tensile Test Samples According to the International Standard (ASTM B557M) (All Dimensions in Millimeters) [12]

Figure 2 Curve Stress and Strain of Aluminum Alloy (2024)

2.3. Fatigue Test

The device used in this research is the Reversed bending machine (HI-TECH) of British origin as shown in Figure (3). All tests were performed at a value of $R = -1$. The test sample is exposed to a load projected from the left side of the sample gasket perpendicular to the axis of the sample designated for the test. Thus, the sample segment is subjected to the curvature stress and by continuously this opposite curvature with the same value up and down leads to fatigue failure and fracture of the sample. The device is equipped with a meter to record the number of stress cycles. All tests were conducted at a rotational speed of 6000 rpm and a frequency of 60 Hertz.

Figure 3 Fatigue test machine

Figure 4 Types of fatigue model

3. Theoretical analyses

The fatigue process begins with the accumulation of damage in a specific area due to repeated loads, which eventually leads to the formation of cracks and their subsequent spread. When one of the cracks grows to a certain extent so that the remaining net portion is not sufficient to bear the applied load, a sudden fracture occurs. In the absence of significant internal defects (large impurities), fatigue cracks usually begin on the surface of the sample and their initial growth is generally in the direction of the greatest strain of sternum. Generally the sites of the beginning of the cracks are either very prior stressful areas such as cracks, craters, scratches or valley-like surface cracks, so by viewing the surface of fatigue fracture we may distinguish three features [13].

- Crack initiation
- Crack Propagation
- Sudden Fracture

3.1. The notch and stress concentration

The openings are used for practical purposes and to reduce the weight of the structures for spacecraft or aircraft, that the presence of these openings plays an important role in the design of mechanical structures and the weakening of their behavior, which leads to a redistribution of stresses in the plate that leads to a significant reduction in the stability of the structure, which drew the attention of many researchers in past years. The holes in the engineering designs constitute one of the complex problems facing the designer due to the areas of focus stress local near these openings resulting from the areas of the presence of these holes. These openings become strainer lever areas. The stress concentration is attributed only to the different sections of the shape, the discontinuity of the fixed geometrical shape, and the decrease in the total area [14].

4. Numerical analysis

4.1. Development of a fatigue model for aluminum alloys.

The general analysis using ANSYS workbench) contains six main steps:

- Define element type.
- Engineering data.
- Geometry.

- Mesh The Model geometry.
- Boundary condition.
- Fatigue solution.

Figure 5 ANSYS Sample without Notches

Figure 6 ANSYS Sample notch analysis

4.2. Mesh the model geometry

For this work, the number of elements was (3204) elements with the total number of nodes (17138) knots for the model that does not contain Notch slits) as shown in Figure (7). In the current work, the appropriate size of the grid was 0.9) mm as shown in Table (3). And the number of elements is 3105, with a total number of nodes (16669) knots for contain at notches as shown in figure (8).

Table 3 Grid independent test (GIT)

Mesh size(mm)	0.5	0.9	1.2	1.5	2	3	4	5
Stress (MPa)	81.35	80.931	79.472	79.574	78.678	83.161	84.374	84.426

Figure 7 Mesh (without Notch)

Figure 8 Mesh (with Notch)

4.3. Boundary condition

The next step involved applying appropriate boundary conditions and external loads. The force in ANSYS Workbench will be on one side, and the other side will be fixed support as shown in Figure (9). As for the shape (10), which contains notch, the force is far from the slitting by (50) mm.

Figure 9 Fixed support and applying load

Figure 10 Fixed support and load with notch

4.4. Fatigue Solution

The fatigue results can be obtained from selection fatigue tool and insert life option at different loads in Ansys15.0 workbench.

In order to complete the total solution of any case, other important parameters are added, such as mass density, Poisson ratio, ultimate stress, tensile yield stress and experimental S-N curves, and Young’s modulus [15] as shown in the table (4).

Table 4 Properties Insert to ANSYS (Obtain from Experimental Work

Type of series	σ_y (MPa)	σ_u (MPa)	E (GPa)	Poisons Ratio
o-2024	73.6	195.2	69	0.33

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Fatigue test results (Experimental)

Fatigue test results were performed for two conditions, baseline samples, and median slitting samples. The stress ratio for all tests was R = -1 at a frequency of (60 Hz), and all tests were performed at a rotational speed of 6000 rpm. The practical side is divided as follows.

- Basic Material without Notch.
- Samples containing center Hole.

At this stage, we will study comparing samples with median incision with theoretical and practical samples. The load and stress of the basic samples can be calculated from the following equations mentioned in the device manual.

$$\sigma_b = \frac{6 * L * P}{b * t^3} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

As for finding strength and stress in samples that contain a median groove, it is done from the following equations [16].

$$\sigma_{nom} = \frac{6 * M}{(b - d) * t^2} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

$$\sigma_b = K_t * \sigma_{nom} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

5.1.1. Basic Material without Notch

Table 5 Stress values, deviation, load, and number of cycles for base samples

I	Stress (MPa)	N_f (EXP)
1	80	2163857
2	100	566857
3	123	133768
4	138	93045
5	161	46028
6	169	27175
7	177	20427
8	207	16926
9	230	10865
10	246	3397

Figure 11 Curved (S-N) for baseline samples

Figure 12 The location of the fracture in (BM)

5.1.2. Samples containing center Hole

Table 6 Values of Stress, Deviation, Load, and Number of Cycles of Samples (CH)

I	Stress (MPa)	N_f (EXP)
1	55	1645300
2	71	420870
3	85	113325
4	96	50723
5	112	40323
6	117	26350
7	123	16530
8	144	10199
9	160	5920
10	171	1645

Figure 13 The S-N curve of notched samples (CH)

Figure 14 The location of the fracture in the samples (CH)

5.2. Endurance limit and Fatigue Curve (Experimental)

Depending on the shape of the Basquin equation, the fatigue life equations for constant capacitance loads can be represented by blasting with spheres and without them by the following equation

The fatigue curve can be presented by the following equation [17]:

$$\sigma_f = A (N_f)^m \quad \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

Where: σ_f is the applied stress (MPa) at failure?

N_f : is the fatigue life (cycles).

A and m : material constants and may be evaluated by linearizing

Then equation (7) can be written in logarithmic form (15), as follows:

$$\text{Log}\sigma_f = \text{Log}A + m\text{Log}N_f \quad \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

Figure 15 Is a logarithmic description of the life fatigue equation [15]

From these equations, fatigue strength was extracted after substituting $N_f = (10^6)$ in the mentioned equations. Note that streaking reduces fatigue resistance by (35%) from base samples and Table (7) shows the practical fatigue curve equations.

Table 7 The equations for practical fatigue values

Material	Curve Equation	Fatigue Limit
BM	$\sigma_f = 1191.8N_f^{-0.187}$	58.5
CH	$\sigma_f = 687.41N_f^{-0.176}$	40

5.3. Numerical Analysis

5.3.1. Basic samples (BM)

Figures (16) to (19) show Equivalent Stress, Safety Factor, total deformation and number of cycles for base samples at stress (80 MPa), and other samples were calculated in the same way shown in Table (8).

Figure 16 Von Mises Stress

Figure 17 Total deformation for

Figure 18 The Safety Factor

Figure 19 Available for Fatigue life

Table 8 The theoretical values through the ANSYS program

Applied stress (MPa)	Total deformation (mm)	Equivalent stress (MPa)	N. of cycle to failure (NUM)	Safety factor
80	0.792	81	2018700	0.986
100	1.020	104	511050	0.766
123	1.239	124.6	127970	0.631
138	1.388	140.17	88832	0.563
161	1.615	163.53	44124	0.484
169	1.685	171.32	25354	0.4641
177	1.784	179.11	20084	0.438
207	2.081	210.26	16303	0.375
230	2.304	233.62	9984.1	0.339
246	2.477	249.19	0	0.315

Figure 20 The location of the fraction for the baseline samples

5.3.2. Samples containing CH

Figures (21) to (24) show Equivalent Stress, Safety Factor, total deformation and number of cycles for samples containing a median groove of 1 mm in diameter (171 MPa), and other samples were calculated in the same way and their values are shown in Table (9).

Figure 21 Equivalent (Von Mises) Stress

Figure 22 (Safety Factor)

Figure 23 (Total deformation)

Figure 24 The (N. of life for)

Table 9 The theoretical values for samples (CH)

Applied stress (MPa)	Total deformation (mm)	Equivalent stress (MPa)	N. of cycle to failure (NUM)	Safety factor
55	0.795	124.31	1723600	1.025
71	1.024	159.68	427980	0.796
85	1.249	191.38	114950	0.652
96	1.392	215.3	53891	0.585
112	1.606	251.19	41115	0.507
117	1.690	263.15	28695	0.482
123	1.785	275.11	18274	0.456
144	2.088	322.95	11026	0.390
160	2.286	358.84	6029.4	0.356
171	2.498	382.76	1735.1	0.326

Figure 25 The fractional location between Experimental and theoretical for CH

5.4. Endurance limit and Fatigue Curve (NUM)

Thus reducing the number of cycles and reducing fatigue resistance by (34.86%) from the base samples. The fatigue curve equations are shown in Table (10).

Table 10 The equations for the fatigue curve (theoretical)

Material	Curve Equation (NUM)	Fatigue Limit
BM	$\sigma_f = 1190.2N^{-0.185}$	60.34
CH	$\sigma_f = 662.16N^{-0.175}$	39.4

6. The comparison between Experimental and theoretical.

The results showed that the compatibility is good between theoretical and practical, but there is a slight difference in the number of calculated cycles between practical and theoretical, which is less than 10% and is acceptable, and the reason is due to the discrepancy between practical and theoretical values due to the state of the process, which cannot be controlled and also was not accurate due to the equipment and the environment.

Table 11 The difference between theoretical and Experimental samples (BM)

Stress (MPa)	N_f (EXP)	N_f (NUM)	Error%
80	2163857	2010400	7
100	566857	511050	9.84
123	133768	127970	4.33
138	93045	88832	4.52
161	46028	44124	4.13
169	27175	25354	6.7
177	20427	20084	1.68
207	16926	16303	3.68
230	10865	9984.1	8.1
246	3397	0	1

Table 12 The difference between theoretical and Experimental samples (CH)

Stress (MPa)	N_f (EXP)	N_f (NUM)	Error%
55	1645300	1723600	4.54
71	420870	427980	1.66
85	113325	114950	1.41
96	50723	53891	5.87
112	40323	41115	1.92
117	26350	28695	8.17
123	16530	18274	9.54
144	10199	11026	7.5
160	5920	6029.4	1.81
171	1645	1735.1	5.19

Nomenclature

Symbols	
F	Force, N
σ	Stress, MPa
A	Area, m^2
ε	Strain,
L	Length, mm
E	Modulus of elasticity, GPa
P	The Load, N
b	Width, mm
T	thickness, mm
Δ	deflection, mm

σ_b	Stress bending, MPa
M	Moment of inertia, N.mm
D	Diameter of Hole, mm

7. Conclusion

- The more stress on the samples, the less the number of cycles, and consequently, the sample will be broken and failure will occur.
- Grooving in the samples works to focus the stress and thus increase the stress value that causes the failure process faster than the base samples.
- Through the equations we note that the grooves reduce the fatigue resistance by (35%) of the base samples in the practical part, while in the theoretical part we notice that the grooves reduce the fatigue resistance by (34.86%) of the core samples.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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